

Party Affiliation of Youths, Political Behaviour and Perceived Effects of Voter Preparedness and Active Participation on Democratic Processes in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined party affiliations of youths, political behaviour and perceived effects of voter preparedness, active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study adopted mixed methods of opinion survey research and ex-post facto designs to examine the influence of party affiliations on the perceptions and political behaviour of youths; and perceived effects of voter preparedness, active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A sample of 500 youth party members was selected using multistage sampling comprising simple random sampling, cluster sampling and purposive sampling techniques to select 5 local Government Areas, 10 wards and 50 youths per ward respectively. A 30-item 3-point modified Likert-type questionnaire instrument titled 'Party affiliation of youths and perceived effects of voter preparedness and active participation on democratic processes' (PAYPEVPAPDP) in Bayelsa state; with 3 subscales was developed, validated and tested for reliability with Spearman-Brown Split-half formula yielding 0.78, 0.68 and 0.81 for subscales 1, 2, and 3 respectively. Ethical considerations were observed as the instrument was administered to youths between the ages of 20 and 35 years and collated data analysed with percentage presented in bar chart and chi-square summaries at 5% level of significance. Results of the study showed strong associations of party affiliations of youths with their political perceptions and behaviour ($X^2 = 31.2051$) and critical $X^2 = 15.51$; strong associations between party affiliations and perceived effects of voter preparedness at ($X^2 = 45.7585$) and critical $X^2 = 15.51$; as well as strong associations between party affiliation of youths and perceived effects of active and responsible participation at ($X^2 = 48.4246$) and critical $X^2 = 15.51$. Compositely, there was perceived positive effects of voter preparedness, active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes among youths of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that pre-election voter preparedness, active and responsible participation among voters should be ensured by a special agency designated and empowered with special duties to enlighten, educate and prepare voters' mind-sets towards voting constitutionally, to sustain democratic values among youths irrespective of whatever party affiliations they may have.

Keywords: Party Affiliation of Youths, Political Perception and Behaviour, Voter Preparedness and Democratic Processes, Active and Responsible Voting.

1. Introduction

Democracy in Nigeria can be called many things, as there appears to be a lot of power play and manipulations influencing the final outcome of each electoral process. The reality in Nigeria's democratic processes sometimes turns out to be injurious, causing mayhem to human lives and properties. Politicians are the first to be blamed for electoral violence and public opinion have them cast in the role of villains, except that they are not the only culprits to be blamed for most of the insecurity experienced during elections. Incumbent administrations, the judiciary, the Independent

National Electoral Commission (INEC), security agents, electoral laws guiding political conduct of politicians and the electoral process; as well as voters are sometimes responsible for the actions leading to continuous spate of violence during elections.

In Nigeria, the youths are oftentimes seen as stooges used by politicians to create inter-party rivalry and fuel violence among the electorate. This is attributed to wrong perceptions and political behaviour of youths in Nigeria. Electoral processes are key democratic processes in Nigeria and have in the recent past been therefore characterized by violence, fraud, rivalry, rigging, vote buying, ballot boxes theft, results annulments as well as post-election litigations (Aluagba, 2016; Ayinde, 2019; Mojishola, 2024; Okafor & Okafor, 2018; Sakariyau et al, 2015; Sule et al, 2017; Yemi-Fadipe & Fasae, 2022). Some of these reasons have been attributed to causing political apathy and alienation in Nigeria, including Bayelsa state. In Bayelsa and some other states, many people have been less actively involved in general elections as they have lost confidence in some political leaders and the electoral system leading to their election (Ekot & Momoh, 2024; Adedoyin-Jolaade & Ojibara, 2017). After the 2023 presidential elections in Bayelsa state, many young people expressed their disappointment with the results because they did not believe it represented the actual voting at the polling stations. Some youths have started to perceive that the electoral system has failed to help them select the right leaders as they felt that their votes did not count during the democratic process.

Youths can be described as young people with the physical characteristics and intellect of young adults, aged between 20 and 35 years. The Commonwealth Youth Programme (the Commonwealth, 2023) describes youths as all young people between the ages of 15 and 29 years which constitute about 1.5 billion youths; while the National Youth Policy Document of Nigeria (National Youth Council of Nigeria [NYCN], 2019) stipulates that youths shall comprise all males and females between the ages of 18 and 29 years. The United Nations (UNESCO, 2012) also defines youths to comprise young women and men between the ages of 15 and 24, while the African Youth Charter defined youths to include individuals between ages 15 and 35. However, the word 'youth' connotes young adulthood and does not include teenagers but at the age when most young people begin to identify themselves as individuals capable of asserting self-determination, social statuses and independence from family grip. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, a youth is defined as an individual between the ages of 20 and 35. In Nigeria, the youth population remains significantly influential to political participation as most of the people actively involved in party politics, electoral violence and fraud such as rigging, ballots theft and votes buying are youths working for the political elite.

Democratic processes in Nigeria start with registration of political parties and candidates' selection through party primaries, registration of voters, materials and appointment of electoral officers working with the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), active voting, counting and the declaration of results. In Nigeria, democratic processes mostly end up in litigations which could be avoided if the electorate is well prepared and equipped with the right mindset. Sustainable democracy should therefore depend largely on voter preparedness, active participation and responsible voting as these would change the perception and behaviour of the electorate, especially among the youth population.

Voter preparedness is therefore aimed at providing education to coach, guide, counsel and train voters on democratic rights and activities prior to; and during elections. It also includes guidelines on voting and electoral intelligence, franchise rights and anti-violence strategies to counter electoral violence and fraud. Thus voter preparedness is not aimed at countering violence with violence but at being proactive, organised and resistant to schemes employed by political thugs; and to stop votes buying or sales of individual permanent voters' cards (PVCs). Thus it has been described as a tool for credible elections in Nigeria by many scholars (Muhammed & Faruk, 2022; Salawudeen, 2025; Yemi-Fadipe & Fasae, 2022).

Active participation and responsible voting is a conscious and conscientious voter-activeness which signifies thoughtful reflections on candidates' character, credibility, party affiliation, ideology and manifesto. Responsible voting implies voting the right candidate not according to party, ethnic or religious affiliations; or financial benefits but for the candidate's character and ideologies. Active participation is the lawful involvement of eligible voters in democratic processes according to the Nigerian constitution. Party affiliation of voters may have very strong influences on the way voters perceive the voting process and their voting responsibilities. How voters perceive these democratic processes and how these perceptions affect the outcome of each election in Nigeria is determined by many factors. Therefore, voters' perception of effects of these characteristics on democratic processes goes a long way to promote or hinder sustainable democracy in Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Party Affiliations and Political Perception and Behaviour of Youths

Studies of party affiliations and political perception and behaviour of voters have influenced diverse outcomes of democratic processes in Nigeria. Youths as the major active players in democratic evolution and development, on the

African continent have played a gigantic role in stabilising or destabilising democratic processes. In Nigeria, party affiliations of youths have gone a long way to influence their political perception and behaviour and thereby change the political landscape either positively or negatively. However, some people believe youth perception and behaviour to be changing for good in the positive direction (Mojishola, 2024; Nkwede, 2015). Paudel et al (2018) posited that social media communication impacts perception of many people and the voting behaviour of youths because of the political influence it exerts on the polity in advancing party empathy or apathy as the case may be.

However, the attitude of youths towards party politics is not always agreeable as they perceive political parties and politicians as the cause of so many societal issues which are detrimental to youth empowerment. People see youths as disadvantaged in politics because they are often manipulated by older political party members to behave as goons perpetrating violence instead of portraying themselves as potential leaders (Ekot & Momoh, 2024; Kofi & Ibanga, 2018) According to Namu et al, (2024) youth political perception and behaviour in Nigeria is determined by 11% party affiliation, 15% party policies, 4% candidate's personality and 15% religious affiliations.

Paudel et al (2018) examined political party perception and voting behaviour of Nepalese using mixed designs comprising descriptive for factual data description and causal-comparative design for identifying cause and effect relations between independent and dependent variables. A sample of 333 of mixed voters was selected using multistage sampling comprising simple random and purposive sampling techniques and a Likert-type questionnaire instrument with a Cronbach reliability of 0.83 developed to collect data on factors impacting political perception and voting behaviour of Nepalese people. Analysed data using frequencies and percentages as well as inferential statistics comprising dependent t-test and regression inferential showed social media enhanced political party perception and significant relationship between political party perception and political interest, political trust, religion and use of social media.

Similarly, Namu et al (2024) examined the relationship between social media and youths voting behaviour in Nigeria and found social media to influence youth political perception and behaviour. The study used mixed approaches of qualitative and quantitative methods and survey design with a sample of 213 students selected with convenience sampling technique. A self developed Likert-type questionnaire was used to collect data on influence of social media on the voting behaviour of Nigerian students in the 2023 presidential elections. Analysed data showed that social media influences the political perceptions of youths and their political behaviour positively; as well as negatively to an extent.

Kofi and Ibanga (2018) also examined youth perception and electoral behaviour in Akwa-Ibom state, Nigeria using both qualitative and quantitative methods as well as historical, descriptive survey and ex-post facto designs to elicit empirical data. The mixed designs were used to allow the researcher explore both existing and empirical data to be retrieved for analysis. A sample of 370 youths was selected using stratified random sampling and a self-made questionnaire instrument designed to collate data on youth political perception and behaviour. Data analysis of percentage and chi-square showed youth perception of politics and political behaviour to be tilted towards the use of violence and coercion to win elections; as well as significant relationships between youth perception of politics, electoral misconduct and violent behaviour.

Similarly, Idowu and Iyabode (2024) examined the voting patterns and behaviour of the electorate during the 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria and discovered that the voting pattern of the Nigerian electorate is grossly influenced by ethnic, religious, regional and party affiliations and sentiments. The study used mixed methods of qualitative and quantitative research survey and direct participant observation to collect data as well as primary and secondary sources comprising interviews, newspaper and online sources. Analysed data showed Nigerian elections lack international approved standards and integrity as well as the credibility it required to be truly democratic in the global community. Youth perception and behaviour in Nigeria have therefore impacted on democratic processes as most studies portray youth perception and political behaviour to be influenced by party affiliation, loyalty and material gain. However, not all youths perceive politics in the same way.

Nkwede (2015) also examined the determinants of voter behaviour in the 2015 Ebonyi state gubernatorial elections in Nigeria using quasi-experimental survey design and observation as well as interviews through primary and secondary sources. The results of the study showed that contrary to common belief and past findings, voter behaviour and participation in Nigeria is greatly influenced by party affiliations, manifestoes, policies and programmes rather than personal gratification.

Thus, research has shown youth perception, political behaviour and participation to be greatly influenced by their party affiliation and the type of political ideology sold to them; such as violence and material inducements and money politics.

2.2 Voter Preparedness and Democratic Processes

Voter preparedness has significant effects on voters' active participation and democratic processes in Nigeria. That is why Osondu (2014) found significant relationships between political mobilization of citizens and political participation in his study in Nigeria. The study examined democratic process and participation of voters in Imo state Nigeria, using a

survey design and stratified random sampling technique to select 150 participants for the study. A self-structured 20-item questionnaire instrument was developed and administered to mixed sections of society, which analysed data showed Nigeria's democratic processes to be grossly influenced by religion, party zoning system, party affiliation, poor preparedness, poor electoral education and mobilisation prior to elections. Thus, the authors attributed these findings to gross disregard of political parties to constitutional provisions as well as lack of proper electoral education and general preparedness.

To explain the gross misconduct exhibited during democratic processes in Nigeria, Yemi-Fadipe and Fasae (2022) posited that Nigerian youths have become pawns in the hands of politicians for their political games. This portrays the need to involve all in democratic processes through voter education. Adedoyin-Jolaade and Ojibara (2017) investigated youth political participation in Kwara state Nigeria, between 2007 and 2015 using a survey research design and simple random sample to select 318 participants and self-structured questionnaire to collect data which results showed youths are not actively involved in political party participation in Kwara state, Nigeria. This calls for urgent reforms to the democratic system in Nigeria because the youths are the future of every nation.

However, Oladejo and Oni (2019) also investigated issues and challenges of political education and community development in Nigeria and found political education to be grossly inadequate. The study used mixed methods comprising survey research and case study design and a self-structured questionnaire instrument to collect data on issues and challenges of implementing democratic education in Nigeria. The study found voter education to be lacking grossly and recommended that it should be a matter of necessity prior to each electoral process to facilitate its successful transition.

Similarly, Ayinde (2019), Muhammed and Faruk (2022) and Oladejo and Oni (2022) identified the relevance of voter education in Nigeria's democratic process, as a credible tool for selecting good leaders and variously advocated for voter education in Nigeria for successful future democratic processes and as means of taking care of the numerous political challenges experienced during elections.

To investigate the relevance of voter education, Salawudeen (2025) carried out a study on the relationship between voter education and awareness among pre-service social studies students in Osun state Nigeria and found voter education and awareness to be grossly inadequate. The study used mixed methods and designs of cross-sectional and descriptive survey and a multistage sampling comprising purposive sampling and stratified sampling technique for selecting institutions and 160 pre-service social studies students. A self-structured questionnaire instrument was developed and used to collect data which results showed gross lack of voter education and awareness among social studies pre-service students.

Most studies therefore support voter education as a means of helping youths understand the rules guiding politics and political participation as well as improving their awareness of voter rights and responsibilities during democratic processes.

2.3 Active and Responsible Voter Participation in Democratic Processes

Active voter participation in democratic processes is imperative for successful democracy. Some researchers have reported low turnout of voters during general elections in Nigeria (Igiebor, 2019; Madu et al, 2024; Yahya, 2023). Low voter participation in Nigeria is attributed to political apathy and alienation (Afolayan, 2018; Yahya, 2023). Voter active participation keeps dwindling over the years since 1999 when Nigeria experienced its first democratic transition without the usual electoral litigations. According to Yahya (2023) political participation in Nigeria was highest in 2003 at 70%, and then 35% in 2019. However, some researchers (Hassan, 2024; Modu et al (2024; Oladipo, 2025) also reported that voter participation in Nigeria keeps declining as democracy progresses over the years; precisely between 1999 and 2023. In 1999 there were 30.2 million active voters out of 58.8 million, and 42 million active voters out of 60.8 million in 2003, 35.3 million active voters out of 61.5 million in 2007, 39.4 million active voters out of 73.5 million in 2011, 29.4 million active voters out of 67.4 million in 2015, 29.3 million active voters out of 82.3 million in 2019; and 24.9 million active voters out of 93.4 in 2023.

Declining political participation in Nigeria is attributed to inadequate voter education, corruption, mismanagement of electoral processes, negation of campaign promises, wrong perception of voters and corrupt practices such as votes buying and selling during elections. To this effect, Igiebor (2022) also investigated political alienation and participation in Nigeria' 2019 general elections and found gradual decline in voter participation. The study used mixed methods of descriptive survey and ex-post facto designs and a sample of 1200 households selected using multistage sampling comprising stratified random sampling and systematic sampling technique to select Local Government Areas and households. A self-structured questionnaire instrument was used, with the results showing voter political absence and inactivity attributed to alienation, bad governance, failure of political leaders to fulfill promises, electoral fraud and electoral violence in Nigeria.

Similarly, Oyewole et al (2024) also investigated effects of active and passive voter political behaviour on government and development in Nigeria using descriptive survey design with a sample of 185 participants selected with accidental sampling technique and a 5-point Likert-type questionnaire instrument which results showed active participation of voters to be influenced by accountability and character of leaders, good governance and development.

Contrary to what many people believe, Aluaigba (2016) averred that lack of active voter participation is as a result of voter apathy for false declaration of winners, rigging and also as a result of the alienation of political parties and their candidates.

Okafor and Okafor (2018) in their study also found high levels of political violence in the South-Eastern parts of Nigeria and averred that this has greatly reduced the credibility of electoral processes and the relevance democracy brings to a nation's global reputation. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design with a multistage sampling comprising random sampling and proportionate stratified random sampling to select states, districts and 750 participants for the study. A self-structured questionnaire instrument was developed to collect data on political violence and prospect for democracy. Collated data was analysed with percentages, Spearman rank order co-efficient, regression and factorial analysis with findings showing significant relationship between political violence and willingness to participate or support democracy.

Similarly, Ganiyu and Hamzat (2020) examined the challenges of voter participation and impact on sustainable democracy using descriptive survey research and a sample of purposively selected 300 respondents for the study. A self-structured questionnaire instrument was developed and validated with a reliability of 0.70 Cronbach alpha; with the results showing political fraud, violence, insecurity, lack of fulfilment on government's part as well as poor preparedness on the part of INEC.

This study therefore sought to determine the relationship between party affiliation of youths and perception of political behaviour and their perceived effects of voter preparedness, active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

3. Methodology

3.1 Variables

The study adopted mixed methods of opinion survey research and ex-post facto designs to examine party affiliation of youths and their political behaviour, perceived effects of voter preparedness, active participation and responsible voting on democratic processes in Bayelsa state, Nigeria.

3.2 Participants

The population for this study comprised all registered political party youths in Selected Local Government Areas (LGA) of Bayelsa State, which stands at 5,100. The sample therefore comprises 500 youths selected using multistage sampling which comprises simple random sampling to select 5 Local Government Areas, cluster sampling to select 2 wards from each LGA constituting 10 political wards as well as stratified random sampling used to select 100 youths from each party, comprising 100 youths selected from 5 LGAs. The multistage sampling simply put, therefore comprises simple random sampling, cluster sampling and stratified random sampling techniques, used to select 500 youths to constitute the final sample which comprised 180 female and 320 males. In constituting the sample, ethical issues were considered as the study only engaged youths between the ages of 20 and 39 and only those who gave their consent were involved as well as complete confidential treatment of data given for strict academic research.

3.3 Measures and Instruments

A self-designed 30-item, 3-point modified Likert-type questionnaire instrument titled 'Party affiliation of youths and perceived effects of voter preparedness and active participation on democratic processes' (PAYPEVPAPDP) in Bayelsa state with three subscales was developed and validated for data collection by the researcher and three other experts in related disciplines. The modified Likert-type questionnaire instrument (PAYPEVPAPDP) sought to collect data on participants' party affiliations, perceptions of political behaviour and participation as well as their perceived effects of voter preparedness, active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa state. The first section of the instrument (PAYPEVPAPDP) sought to measure demographic data of youths and their party affiliations while section B was used to collate data on youth political behaviour and participation as well as their perceived effects of voter preparedness, active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

The PAYPEVPAPDP instrument constitutes three subscales drawn from positively inclined questionnaire items on effects of voter preparedness, active participation and responsible voting on democratic processes in Bayelsa State. The PAYPEVPAPDP instrument was rated with 3 for 'positive effect', 2 for 'neutral effect' (no effect); and 1 for 'negative effect'.

The PAYPEVPAPDP instrument was validated by three experts and tested for reliability using the Pearson Product Moment reliability co-efficient and split-half reliability with Spearman-Brown correction formula yielding 0.78, 0.68 and 0.81 respectively for subscales 1, 2 and 3.

The (PAYPEVPAPDP) instrument was personally administered to the participants by the researcher. The data collected was analysed using percentage, chi-square inferential statistics in bar chart and chi-square summaries respectively.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Results are based on the following research questions used to guide the study:

1. To what extent do party affiliations and perceptions influence the political behaviour and participation of youths in democratic processes in Bayelsa state?

Figure 1: Bar chart summary of percentage distribution of youth party affiliations, perception of political behaviour and participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

To what extent do party affiliations and political behaviour of youths influence their perceived effects of voter preparedness on democratic processes in Bayelsa state?

Figure 2: Bar chart summary of percentage distribution of party affiliations and perceived effects of voter preparedness on democratic process in Bayelsa state

Figure 2: showed the level of influence party affiliation has exerted on perceived effect of voter preparedness on democratic processes in Nigeria. In figure 2 most youths in three political parties were influenced by their party affiliations to perceive voter preparedness as having positive effect on successful democratic processes in Bayelsa state. Thus PDP youths perceived voter preparedness as having positive effect on democratic processes by 63%, APC 60% and LABOUR 49%, while APGA and AD youths perceived voter preparedness as having no (Neutral) effect on democratic processes by 50% and 57% respectively.

To what extent do party affiliations and political behaviour of youths influence their perceived effects of active and responsible participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

Figure 3: Bar chart summary of percentage distribution of party affiliations and perceived effects of voter preparedness on democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

Figure 3 showed the level of influence party affiliation has exerted on perceived effect of active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Nigeria. In figure 3 most youths in three political parties were influenced by their party affiliations to perceive that active and responsible voter participation has positive effect on democratic processes in Bayelsa state. Thus, LABOUR party youths perceived voter active and responsible participation as having positive influence on democratic processes by 56%, APGA 61% and AD 60%, while PDP and APC youths perceived active and responsible voter participation as having no (Neutral) effect on democratic processes by 59% and 30% respectively. Even 25% of APC youths perceive that active and responsible voter participation would harm democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

4.2 Chi-Square Analysis

H01: Youth perception of political behaviour and participation in Bayelsa state is significantly independent of their party affiliations.

Table 1: Chi-square summary of party affiliations and perception of youth political behaviour and participation in Bayelsa State.

Cells	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	46	52	-6	36	0.6925
2	47	52	-5	25	0.4808
3	43	52	-9	81	1.5577
4	60	52	8	64	1.2308
5	64	52	12	144	2.7692
6	43	35.2	7.8	60.84	1.7284
7	40	35.2	4.8	23.04	0.6545
8	31	35.2	-4.2	17.64	0.5011
9	30	35.2	-5.2	27.04	0.7682
10	32	35.2	-3.2	10.24	0.2909
11	11	12.8	-1.8	3.24	0.2531
12	13	12.8	0.2	0.04	0.0031
13	26	12.8	13.2	174.24	13.6125
14	10	12.8	-2.8	7.84	0.6125
15	4	12.8	-8.8	77.44	6.05
Total				X ² =	31.2051

df = 8 at 0.05 α level of significance; critical Chi-Square = 15.51

Decision: the calculated chi-square value of ($X^2 = 31.2051$) is greater than the critical table value (15.51), therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. The perceived effect of responsible voting on democratic processes is significantly dependent on party affiliation of youths in Bayelsa state, Nigeria.

H02: The perceived effect of voter preparedness on democratic processes among youths is significantly independent of party affiliations in Bayelsa state.

Table 2: Chi-square summary of association of party affiliation and perceived effect of voter preparedness on democratic processes in Bayelsa state.

Cells	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	63	47	16	16	5.4468
2	60	47	13	13	3.5957
3	49	47	2	4	0.0851
4	40	47	-7	49	1.0425
5	23	47	-24	576	12.2553
6	31	41	-10	100	2.4390
7	30	41	-11	121	2.9512
8	37	41	-4	16	0.3902
9	50	41	9	81	1.9756
10	57	41	16	256	6.2439
11	6	12	-6	36	3
12	10	12	-2	4	0.3333
13	14	12	2	4	0.3333
14	10	12	-2	4	0.3333
15	20	12	8	64	5.3333
Total				X ² =	45.7585

df = 8 at 0.05 α level of significance; critical chi-square = 15.51

Decision: the calculated chi-square value of ($X^2 = 45.7585$) is greater than the critical table value of 15.51 therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. The perceived effect of voter preparedness on democratic processes is significantly dependent on party affiliation of youths in Bayelsa state.

H02: The perceived effect of active and responsible participation of voters on democratic processes is significantly dependent on party affiliation of youths in Bayelsa state.

Table 3: Chi-square summary of association of party affiliations of youths and perceived effect of active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa State.

Cells	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	31	50.6	-19.6	384.16	7.5921
2	45	50.6	-15.6	31.36	0.6198
3	56	50.6	5.4	29.16	0.5761
4	61	50.6	10.4	108.16	2.1375
5	60	50.6	9.4	88.36	1.7462
6	59	34.4	24.6	605.16	17.5918
7	30	34.4	-4.4	19.36	0.5628
8	35	34.4	0.6	0.36	0.0105
9	22	34.4	-12.4	153.76	4.4698
10	26	34.4	-8.4	70.56	2.0512
11	10	15	-5	25	1.6667
12	25	15	10	100	6.6667
13	9	15	-6	36	2.4
14	17	15	2	4	0.2667
15	14	15	-1	1	0.0667
Total				X ² =	48.4246

df = 8 at 0.05 α level of significance; critical chi-square = 15.51

Decision: the calculated chi-square value ($X^2 = 48.4246$) is greater than the critical table value (15.51), therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. The perceived effect of active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes is significantly dependent on party affiliation of youths in Bayelsa state.

5. Discussion

From the results it can be seen that youths from APGA and AD perceived voter political behaviour and participation has influenced democratic processes positively in Bayelsa state. The popular parties such as PDP and APC and LABOUR perceived political behaviour and participation to have less positive effect on democratic processes as they believed less conventional means would produce more effective results to successful democratic processes in Bayelsa state. This implies that the youths from political parties with less political will to rig have acquired affiliated interest and perception that good political attitude and behaviour influences political participation positively and hence the democratic process. This is corroborated by Kofi and Ibanga (2018) who found youth political party perception to influence their political behaviour and inclined towards using violence and coercion to win elections. Similarly, Idowu and Iyabode (2024) and Nkwede (2015) in their various studies also substantiated these findings in their separate studies which findings showed youth political behaviour to be greatly influenced by party affiliation of youths in Bayelsa state.

So also, youths of the leading political parties perceive voter preparedness as having positive effect on democratic processes in Bayelsa State with PDP and APC topping the list. This is similar to Osondu's (2014) report in her study where it corroborated the findings that there exists significant relationship between political mobilization of citizens in terms of political education and preparedness and successful democratic processes in Nigeria. This was also corroborated by Kofi and Ibanga (2018) who reported that political education of youths has significant influence on their participation during electoral processes, with reference to Akwa-Ibom state, Nigeria. The rest of the youths from other parties think differently and this is attributed to popular belief and findings of studies (Adedoyin-Jolaade & Ojibara, 2017; Okafor & Okafor, 2018; Sakariyau et al, 2015) that most ruling parties rig elections to win and therefore youths from these parties think that voter preparedness will not make any positive difference to those who do not engage in electoral fraud. Youths from the less-popular-political-parties ([LPPP], LABOUR, APGA and AD) think that the leading political parties (LPP) based on past experience always find a way through less conventional means to win elections. Moreover, youths from the LPPP seem to have lost confidence in the electoral system's ability to truly deliver the decision of the electorate.

There was perceived positive effect of active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes in Bayelsa state as most youths from minor political parties (LABOUR, APGA and AD) were influenced by their party affiliations to perceive active and responsible voter participation as having positive effect on democratic processes. However, some of the youths from one of the major parties (PDP) perceive this differently. This result is supported by Oyewole et al (2024) who substantiated that active and responsible political participation of youths is influenced by their party affiliation and perception of leadership credibility and accountability. However, most youths from major political parties think otherwise and this is corroborated by Igiebor (2019) who also found active and responsible political participation to be negatively influenced by party affiliations of youths.

The findings of this study showed strong associations between party affiliations and perception of youths and political behaviour and participation at ($X^2 = 31.2051$) and critical $X^2 = 15.51$, strong associations between party affiliations and perceived effects of voter preparedness and education at ($X^2 = 45.7585$) and critical $X^2 = 15.51$; as well as strong associations between party affiliation of youths and perceived effects of active and responsible voter participation at ($X^2 = 48.4246$) and critical $X^2 = 15.51$. Compositely, perceived effects of political behaviour and participation of youths on democratic processes in Bayelsa state is significantly dependent on party affiliation and perception of youths, that perceived effects of voter preparation and education on democratic processes in Bayelsa state is significantly dependent on party affiliation of youths; as well as perceived effects of active and responsible voter participation on democratic processes is significantly dependent on party affiliation of youths in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Based on these findings, it is therefore recommended that pre-election voter education on positive attitudes and behaviour; and preparedness on positive actions and outcomes; and active and responsible participation among voters should be ensured by a special agency designated; and empowered with special duties to enlighten, educate and prepare voters' mind-sets towards voting constitutionally, to sustain democratic values among youths irrespective of whatever party affiliations they may have.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Youths' perception of effects of voter preparedness, active participation and responsible voting were largely influenced by their political parties' affiliations based on their ideations. Thus, the issues of violence, rigging and money politics are therefore rooted in the parties as to whether the electoral system would work or not. Youths are rather loyal to their parties and follow their party ideologies blindly without questions. Most youths believe that if democracy were allowed to work as it should then there would be sustainable democracy as well as satisfaction across the electorate, hence their perceived positive effects of voter preparedness, active participation and responsible voting on successful democratic process.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Party's should be encouraged to provide value-based manifestoes and ideologies to ensure that party affiliations of youths influence their political perception and behaviour positively
2. Voter preparedness should be done prior to elections and during the campaigning period by a special agency assigned and empowered with this special duty to enlighten, educate, guide and prepare voters' mind-sets towards each democratic process.
3. Active and responsible participation of voters should be encouraged through social campaigns and jingles by a special agency for enlightening and educating the electorate in order to ensure voting rights franchise as well as democratic values in society.

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